

Tehuelche

also known as “Ahonicanka”, “Tchonek”

Data source: eHRAF

Secondary source

Entered by Anj Droë, Human Relations Area Files

** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

** Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA*

Entry tags: South American Religions, Religious Group

The Tehuelche are an indigenous group residing primarily in Patagonia, Argentina and southern Chile. This entry focuses on ethnographic evidence collected during fieldwork with the Tehuelche from 1869-1870, at which time various types of contact between the Tehuelche and the Spanish, including missions and trade relations, had existed for over 300 years (Adem, 2009:1). In 1870, despite centuries of contact with the Spanish, the Tehuelche had maintained their traditional religious beliefs and practices. The Tehuelche believed in both a high god, who had little to do with human affairs, and troublemaking supernatural beings that are also referred to as devils. Religious specialists, who had powers that gave them the ability to treat illnesses, predict the future, and prevent harassment by the devils, played an important role in everyday life. For the Tehuelche, religious beliefs were inseparable from almost all aspects of social and political life. Therefore, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society at large.

Date Range: 1855 CE - 1880 CE

Region: Equestrian Band, ca. 170

Region tags: South America, Argentina, Chile, Patagonia

Tehuelche Equestrian Band, Patagonia, ca. 1870

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. *World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research*.
- Source 2: Murdock, George P. 1962-1971. *Ethnographic Atlas*. *Ethnology* 1-10.
- Source 3: Murdock, George P., and Suzanne F. Wilson. 1972. "Settlement patterns and community organization: Cross-cultural codes 3." *Ethnology* 11, no. 3: 254-295.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=sh05-003>
- Source 1 Description: Musters, George Chaworth. 1872. "On the Races of Patagonia." *Journal of the Anthropological Institute of Great Britain and Ireland* Vol. 1: 193-207.

– Source 2 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=sh05-002>

– Source 2 Description: Musters, George Chaworth. 1873. *At Home with the Patagonians*. London: J. Murray.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: "The missionaries, Messrs. Schmid and Hart, endeavoured to avail themselves of this opportunity [Tehuelche staying at a trade station in the winter] for essaying the conversion and civilisation of the [Tehuelche]" (Musters, 1873:41-42).

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: "They are very naturally suspicious of strangers, but especially those of [Spanish] origin, or, as they term them, Cristianos. Nor, considering the treatment—treacherous cruelty and knavish vobbery—experienced by them at the hands of the invaders and colonists alternately, is this to be wondered at" (Musters, 1873:195).

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– No

Notes: "They are very naturally suspicious of strangers, but especially those of [Spanish] origin, or, as they term them, Cristianos. Nor, considering the treatment—treacherous cruelty and knavish vobbery—experienced by them at the hands of the invaders and colonists alternately, is this to be wondered at" (Musters, 1873:195).

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Notes: "They are very naturally suspicious of strangers, but especially those of [Spanish] origin, or, as they term them, Cristianos. Nor, considering the treatment—treacherous cruelty and knavish vobbery—experienced by them at the hands of the invaders and colonists alternately, is this to be wondered at" (Musters, 1873:195).

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1649, Frequency of Internal Warfare (Resolved Rating), "Internal warfare seems to occur once every 2 years (original code 3)" (Ember and Ember, 1992; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1650, Frequency of External Warfare (Resolved Rating), "External warfare seems to occur at least once every two years (original code 3)" (Ember and Ember 1992; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: Because religious beliefs are inseparable from almost all aspects of social and political life, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society itself. Membership is consequently assumed to be assigned at birth.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: Because religious beliefs are inseparable from almost all aspects of social and political life, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society itself. Therefore, it is assumed that the religion has political support.

Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

Notes: Ethnographic evidence refers to the head of the polity and the head of the religion as separate figures: "The position of wizard or doctor is not a very desirable one, as in the event of his prognosticating a success in a war expedition, or cessation in sickness, or any other event which is not realised, the chief will not unfrequently have him killed" (Musters, 1872:203).

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 1500

Notes: "... the number of the pure Tehuelches, both northern and southern, in Patagonia does not exceed 1,500 men, women, and children ... " (Musters, 1873:73).

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "To propitiate or drive away this [evil] spirit [Gualichu] is the function of the wizard, or doctor, or medicine man, who combines the medical and magical arts, though not possessed of an exclusive faculty for either" (Musters, 1873:189).

Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: "... [Gualichu, the central evil non-human supernatural being] is only prevented from

causing continual annoyance by the spells of the doctors, which latter are not only supposed to be gifted with the power of laying the devil, but also affirm that they can see him" (Musters, 1872:202).

↳ Powers are inherited:

– No

Notes: "Wizards are chosen not by hereditary descent, but by peculiarities exhibited in their youth" (Musters, 1872:203).

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

Notes: "Wizards are chosen not by hereditary descent, but by peculiarities exhibited in their youth" (Musters, 1872:203).

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that if religious practitioners give the wrong advice, they are considered to be at fault and are subsequently punished: "The position of wizard or doctor is not a very desirable one, as in the event of his prognosticating a success in a war expedition, or cessation in sickness, or any other event which is not realised, the chief will not unfrequently have him killed" (Musters, 1872:203).

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that if religious practitioners give the wrong advice, they are considered to be at fault and are subsequently punished: "The position of wizard or doctor is not a very desirable one, as in the event of his prognosticating a success in a war expedition, or cessation in sickness, or any other event which is not realised, the chief will not unfrequently have him killed" (Musters, 1872:203).

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: According to Murdock and Wilson (1972, Column 6, Large or Impressive Structures), "There are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings" (Murdock and Wilson, 1972:259,272; note: equivalent to SCCS variable 66).

Is iconography present:

– No

Notes: "They have no idols or objects of worship . . ." (Musters, 1873:189).

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that the Tehuelche perform small-scale rituals at places believed to be inhabited by previously human spirits: "... there are many others which are supposed to inhabit subterranean dwellings, underneath certain woods and rivers and peculiarly-shaped rocks. I was very much surprised at seeing the Indians salute these objects by placing the hand to the head and muttering an incantation ... subsequently I learned that they sought thus to conciliate the spirits of these places, reputed to be the spirits of deceased members of the faculty" (Musters, 1873:190).

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that the Tehuelche perform small-scale rituals at places believed to be inhabited by previously human spirits: "... there are many others which are supposed to inhabit subterranean dwellings, underneath certain woods and rivers and peculiarly-shaped rocks. I was very much surprised at seeing the Indians salute these objects by placing the hand to the head and muttering an incantation ... subsequently I learned that they sought thus to conciliate the spirits of these places, reputed to be the spirits of deceased members of the faculty" (Musters, 1873:190).

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: "The body is sewn up in a mantle, poncho, or coat of mail, if the deceased possessed one, and is taken away by some of the relations and buried in a sitting posture, its face to the east, a cairn of stones being erected over the place, varying in size according to the wealth and influence of the deceased" (Musters, 1873:187).

Interment:

– Yes

Notes: "The body is sewn up in a mantle, poncho, or coat of mail, if the deceased possessed one, and is taken away by some of the relations and buried in a sitting posture, its face to the east, a cairn of stones being erected over the place, varying in size according to the wealth and influence of the deceased" (Musters, 1873:187).

Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– Yes

Notes: "The body is sewn up in a mantle, poncho, or coat of mail, if the deceased possessed one, and is taken away by some of the relations and buried in a sitting posture, its face to the east, a cairn of stones being erected over the place, varying in

size according to the wealth and influence of the deceased" (Musters, 1873:187).

Secondary burial:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1850, Secondary Bone/Body Treatment, "secondary contact with the body or bones of the deceased does not occur" (Schroeder, 2001; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: "On the death of a Tehuelche all his horses, dogs, and other animals are killed . . ." (Musters, 1872:201).

Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Notes: "On the death of a Tehuelche all his horses, dogs, and other animals are killed . . ." (Musters, 1872:201).

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of grave goods.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: "The body, sown up in a mantle, poncho, or coat of mail, if the deceased possessed one, is taken away by some of the relations, and buried in a sitting posture with its face to the east, a cairn of stones being generally erected over the place" (Musters, 1872:201).

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of a supreme high god, previously human spirits, and non-human supernatural beings, primarily devils or evil spirits (see Musters, 1872:202-204 for more information). However, supernatural beings are not described in substantial detail.

A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 238, High Gods, a supreme high god is "Present but not active in human affairs" (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to

Ethnographic Atlas column 34).

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: "... but there is no doubt that they do believe in a good Spirit [in reference to the supreme high god], though they think he lives 'careless of mankind'" (Musters, 1873:189).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: "... there are many others which are supposed to inhabit subterranean dwellings, underneath certain woods and rivers and peculiarly-shaped rocks. I was very much surprised at seeing the Indians salute these objects by placing the hand to the head and muttering an incantation . . . subsequently I learned that they sought thus to conciliate the spirits of these places, reputed to be the spirits of deceased members of the faculty" (Musters, 1873:190).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: "The belief which prompts all their religious acts is that in the existence of many active and malicious evil spirits or demons, of whom the principal one [Gualichu] is always on the watch to cause mischief" (Musters, 1873:189).

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that some religious specialists have the ability to see evil non-human supernatural beings: "... [Gualichu, the main evil non-human supernatural being] is only prevented from causing continual annoyance by the spells of the doctors, which latter are not only supposed to be gifted with the power of laying the devil, but also affirm that they can see him" (Musters, 1872:202).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "This household devil is, as far as I could ascertain, supposed to enter into the different parts of the bodies of people, and cause sickness which the doctor is appealed to to cure" (Musters, 1873:189).

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of a supreme high god, previously

human spirits, and non-human supernatural beings, primarily devils or evil spirits (see Musters, 1872:202-204 for more information).

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of supernatural monitoring.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of sex restrictions.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of sex restrictions.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Yes

Notes: "Both sexes tattoo on the forearm, by the simple process of puncturing the skin with a bodkin, and inserting a mixture of blue earth with a piece of dry glass: the usual patterns consist of a series of parallel lines, and sometimes a single triangle, or a double triangle, the upper one resting on the apex of the lower. I myself had one line tattooed by a fair enslaver, and confess that the process was rather painful" (Musters, 1873:172).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: "All sacrifices of mares and horses, not at stated times, but as occasion requires, such as a birth, death, &c., are intended to propitiate the Gualichu [evil spirit]" (Musters, 1873:188).

Destroyed:

– Yes

Notes: "All sacrifices of mares and horses, not at stated times, but as occasion requires, such as a birth, death, &c., are intended to propitiate the Gualichu [evil spirit]" (Musters, 1873:188).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: "More important was the destruction of items of prestige in ceremonial contexts. De Viedma (1836:78) mentions the ritual killing of the horse in a variety of ceremonies associated with marriage, death, loss of teeth among children, female puberty rites, bad illnesses, difficulty encountered in hunting, preparation for combat, and placation of the gods" (Musters, 1872:93). Ethnographic indicates that both small-scale and large-scale rituals are present: "However, it is necessary to distinguish between rituals associated with the entire band as opposed to those associated with the individual or toldo" (Musters, 1872:93).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: "More important was the destruction of items of prestige in ceremonial contexts. De Viedma (1836:78) mentions the ritual killing of the horse in a variety of ceremonies associated with marriage, death, loss of teeth among children, female puberty rites, bad illnesses, difficulty encountered in hunting, preparation for combat, and placation of the gods" (Musters, 1872:93). Ethnographic indicates that both small-scale and large-scale rituals are present: "However, it is necessary to distinguish between rituals associated with the entire band as opposed to those associated with the individual or toldo" (Musters, 1872:93).

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of multiple extra-ritual in-group markers, including tattooing, face and body paint, uncut hair, traditional dress, and ornamentation. See questions below for details.

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– Yes

Notes: "Both sexes tattoo on the forearm, by the simple process of puncturing the skin with a bodkin, and inserting a mixture of blue earth with a piece of dry glass: the usual patterns consist of a series of parallel lines, and sometimes a single triangle, or a double triangle, the upper one resting on the apex of the lower" (Musters, 1873:172).

↳ Hair:

– Yes

Notes: "They [the Tehuelche] never cut their hair . . ." (Musters, 1873:xiv).

↳ Dress:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of traditional dress. See Musters, 1872:196-197 for more information.

↳ Ornaments:

– Yes

Notes: "The women are fond of ornaments consisting of huge earrings and necklaces of silver or blue beads; the men also wear these necklaces, and adorn their knife sheaths, belts, and horse gear with silver studs or plate, and such as can afford it indulge in silver spurs and stirrups" (Musters, 1872:196-197).

↳ Other:

– Yes [specify]: Paint

Notes: "After the hair-brushing is finished, the women adorn the men's faces with paint; if in mourning they put on black paint, and if going to fight, sometimes put a little white paint under the eyes, which assists, in contrast to the other, in giving a savage expression. The women paint each other's faces, or if they possess a small piece of looking-glass, paint their own" (Musters, 1872:197).

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A band

Notes: The Tehuelche do not have jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004). Murdock and Wilson (1972; Column 10: Descent) indicate that the Tehuelche have bilateral descent without kindreds. Additionally, the Tehuelche live in agamous communities without localized clans, lineal kin groups, or exogamy (Murdock, 1962-1971, columns 19, 20, 22). Information on jurisdictional hierarchy and kin ties indicates that the Tehuelche are most accurately characterized as a band.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– I don't know

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that wells are dug to provide water in desert areas: "Patricio [an informant] during this day's journey pointed out to me a dry lagoon near which efforts had been made to sink a well for obtaining a permanent supply of water, but, although the shaft was of some depth, none had been reached, and the work had been given up in despair" (Musters, 1873:294).

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 90, Police, police functions are not specialized (Tuden and Marshall, 1972; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 149, Scale 1 [of Cultural Complexity] - Writing and Records, writing

and records are not utilized (Murdock and Provost, 1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: Because the religious group is coterminous with the society itself, this entry assumes that the religious group provides food for itself. The Tehuelche depend primarily on hunting (SCCS Variable 204, Dependence on Hunting), with gathering (SCCS Variable 203, Dependence on Gathering) as a secondary means of subsistence. Fishing (SCCS Variable 205, Dependence on Fishing) supplements the diet (Murdock, 1972-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas column 7).

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing

Notes: The Tehuelche depend primarily on hunting (SCCS Variable 204, Dependence on Hunting), with gathering (SCCS Variable 203, Dependence on Gathering) as a secondary means of subsistence. Fishing (SCCS Variable 205, Dependence on Fishing) supplements the diet (Murdock, 1972-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas column 7).